

SEA WATER RESISTANCE OF MODIFIED POLYCAPROLACTONE

M. Rutkowska, A. Heimowska, K. Krasowska, H. Janik*

Gdynia Maritime Academy, 81-225 Gdynia, Poland

**Technical University of Gdansk, Gdansk, Poland*

SUMMARY: The influence of different processing additives on the resistance of polycaprolactone film in some water environments is described in this paper. Polycaprolactone (PCL) was incubated for several weeks in sea water, liquid medium containing sea water with NaN_3 and buffered salt solution. The loss of weight, intrinsic viscosity, tensile strength and morphological changes were tested during the period of degradation.

INTRODUCTION

Aliphatic polyesters such as polycaprolactone are the most attractive class of artificial polymers, which can degrade in contact with living organisms. The sea water is an example of environment where all kinds of micro and macroorganisms which could be involved in the degradation of polymers are present. According to the literature, degradation of aliphatic polyesters in living environments can result from enzymatic attack or from simple hydrolysis of ester bonds or both¹⁾.

The biodegradation of PCL is known to proceed in at least two distinct stages. The first stage of degradation involves nonenzymatic, random hydrolytic ester cleavage. The initial molecular weight (MW) of polymer as well as its chemical structure determines the duration of first stage. The second stage starts with the slowing down of the rate of chain scission and the beginning of weight loss because of the diffusion of oligomeric species from bulk. The polymer becomes prone to fragmentation and either enzymatic surface erosion or phagocytosis can contribute to the absorption process²⁾.

The aim of this study is an examination of the influence of different processing additives on the resistance of the polycaprolactone film to different water environments.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The observations were done on three different samples of polycaprolactone (MW = 80.000; ρ (23 °C) = 1,145 g/cm³). The samples for our studies are as follows:

- PCL - pure polycaprolactone (Tone 787);
- PCL1 – 90% PCL and 10% NCPE 6271 (commercial additive from Neste containing 7% EBA with antioxidant, antiblock and slip agent)

- PCL2 - 90% PCL and 10% NCPE 5440 (commercial additive from Neste containing 17% EBA with antioxidant, antiblocking, very high slip);

Environments

The incubation of polycaprolactone took place in the Baltic Sea water in Gdynia Harbour, in sea water with NaN_3 in laboratory and in buffered salt solution in laboratory. The incubation lasted for 6 weeks.

The characteristic parameters of sea water environments according to Gdynia Water Management and Meteorology Institute are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters of sea water

PARAMETER	MONTH	
	JULY	AUGUST
TEMPERATURE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	19,3	22,3
pH	8,2	8,8
Cl CONTENT [g/kg]	3,3	3,2
OXYGEN CONTENT [cm^3/dm^3]	7,6	7,4
SALT CONTENT [ppt]	5,9	5,8

The samples were also incubated in sea water with NaN_3 (0,195g / 1l) in laboratory to eliminate the influence of microorganisms onto degradation of polycaprolactone.

Table 2: Parameters of sea water with NaN_3

PARAMETER	MONTH	
	JULY	AUGUST
TEMPERATURE [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	21	20
pH	8,7	8,5

For comparison the hydrolytic degradation of polycaprolactone was studied in a buffered salt solution (pH 7,2) at 37°C . The composition of the buffered salt solution is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Composition of the buffered salt solution

SALT	CONCENTRATION [mg/l]
NaCl	95
KCl	5
NH ₂ C(CH ₂ OH) ₃	30
Ca(CH ₃ COO) ₂ H ₂ O	4
MgSO ₄ *7H ₂ O	2
Na ₂ HPO ₄ *H ₂ O	2
NaN ₃	3

Methods

The changes in weight, the tensile strength, intrinsic viscosity and morphology of polycaprolactone film were tested during experiment.

The weight changes (%) were determined using an electronic balance Gibertini E 42s.

The weight of clean and dried samples of polycaprolactone after biodegradation were compared with that before biodegradation.

Intrinsic viscosity of PCL was measured by means of Ostwald's viscometer at 25°C. The flow time of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30% solution of polycaprolactone in benzene was determined. The variations of specific viscosity as a function of concentration (C) were extrapolated for C=0 and the value of intrinsic viscosity was indicated⁶⁾.

Tensile strength of PCL was measured on Instron 1122 according to Polish Standard⁷⁾.

Microscopic observations of polymer surfaces changes were performed at magnification of 1:300 with methallographic microscope „P 20” linked with video camera using a programme Software VidPres.

Results and discussion

Results of weight changes of polycaprolactone samples during experiment are shown bellow:

Table 4: Weight changes (%) of PCL after incubation in different environments

	ENVIRONMENT	INCUBATION TIME [week]		
		2	4	6
PCL	SEA WATER	-13,9	-40,6	destroyed
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃	-0,4	-0,4	-0,4
	BUFFERED SALT SOLUTION	-3,3	-11,6	-19,8
PCL1	SEA WATER	-1,2	-24,1	-78,7
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃	+0,3	-0,2	-0,2
	BUFFERED SALT SOLUTION	-2,6	-6,9	-10,3
PCL2	SEA WATER	-2,6	-39,2	-90,9
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃	+0,6	-0,5	-0,2
	BUFFERED SALT SOLUTION	-2,6	-8,6	-11,0

[-] - weight loss [%]

[+] - weight increase [%]

The decrease of weight was observed during all the degradation time in every water environment. The weight changes of the sample incubated in sea water with NaN₃ are not significant. It could be explained by only nonenzymatic hydrolytic ester cleavage. In buffered salt solution the changes are more significant, because of higher experimental temperature and more appropriate pH for hydrolytic degradation. In sea water the sample of pure polycaprolactone was degraded very fast and after six weeks was destroyed completely. The samples with processing additives (PCL1 and PCL2) were degraded slower.

During two first weeks of experiment the decrease of weight of PCL1 and PCL2 (with processing additives) in sea water was similar to change of weight in buffered salt solution. This suggests that hydrolytic degradation takes place in the first stage. After four weeks it is seen very clearly that in sea water the weight was decreasing dramatically (the second stage - enzymatic degradation). This can be explained by strong enzymatic attack of living organisms. In the sea all kinds of living organisms which could be involved in the degradation of polymers are present. After six weeks the samples almost lost their weight however the presence of processing additives makes the degradation weaker.

The changes of intrinsic viscosity of polycaprolactone after degradation are giving information about changes of molecular weight. The characteristic parameters are shown in Table 5. The longer the incubation time in microbially active environment the higher the decrease of viscosity of biodegraded pure polycaprolactone. It could be the result of decrease of molecular weight of polycaprolactone. The changes in molecular weight are less significant for polycaprolactone with additives especially in two first weeks. From the data we can also state that the presence of processing additives postpones biodegradation of polycaprolactone.

Table 5: Changes of intrinsic viscosity of polycaprolactone after incubation in different environments

	ENVIRONMENT	INCUBATION TIME [week]			
		0	2	4	6
PCL	SEA WATER	0,0104	0,0025	0,0017	-
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃		0,0099	0,0075	0,0072
PCL1	SEA WATER	0,0108	0,0094	0,0053	-
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃		0,0106	0,0088	0,0082
PCL2	SEA WATER	0,0089	0,0084	0,0064	-
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃		0,0161	0,0109	0,0100

Results of tensile strength of polycaprolactone sample after biodegradation are shown below:

Table 6: Tensile strength $\hat{\alpha}$ [MPa] of PCL samples after incubation in different environments

	ENVIRONMENT	INCUBATION TIME [week]			
		0	2	4	6
PCL	SEA WATER	19,5	-	-	-
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃		15,3	14,3	13,3
	BUFFERED SALT SOLUTION		10,4	10,1	5,6 (10 weeks)
PCL1	SEA WATER	23,7	-	-	-
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃		22,4	23,5	18,3
	BUFFERED SALT SOLUTION		14,1	10,1	10,4
PCL2	SEA WATER	20,2	11,2	-	-
	SEA WATER WITH NaN ₃		15,2	14,8	13,3
	BUFFERED SALT SOLUTION		11,1	8,4	7,5

The decrease in tensile strength of PCL samples after biodegradation can be observed explicitly, which is associated with molecular weight. The results confirm that the first stage of degradation (nonenzymatic hydrolysis) causes the similar decrease in tensile strength in every environment. In the second stage (enzymatic degradation) the decrease in tensile strength is dramatic in microbially active environment - cutting up samples in pieces (in sea water after four weeks). In buffered salt solution the changes are smaller than in sea water with NaN₃. It confirms the results of loss weight and intrinsic viscosity.

Microscopical observations show deterioration of polycaprolactone surface in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The surface of PCL samples before degradation (blind) and after incubation in sea water

Figure 2: The surface of PCL samples before degradation (blind) and after incubation in sea water with NaN_3

After two weeks of biodegradation in microbially active environments we can observe the increase of orientated birefringence elements, which could be an evidence of crystallinity increase. It confirms that amorphous phase is attacked first. After four weeks of experiment the crystalline phase is becoming less visible (less orientated birefringence elements). After six weeks we can see very distinctly the black area which could be nonbirefringent part of the sample after attack and an agglomeration of microorganisms.

The incubation in sea water with NaN_3 does not change samples with processing additives too much even after 36 weeks. Only for the pure polycaprolactone sample we can observe the changes of the surface, even the changes of weight and tensile strength are not very distinctive.

Conclusion

The changes in weight, intrinsic viscosity, tensile strength and microscopical observations after incubation of polycaprolactone with processing additives in sea water environments lead to conclusion that the biodegradation of polycaprolactone occurs in two stages.

The first stage (nonenzymatic hydrolysis) consists of waterdiffusion into the amorphous phase with hydrolytic random ester cleavage. Hydrolytic attack then progresses within crystalline aggregates and the second stage (enzymatic degradation) starts with the slowing down of the rate of chain scission and the onset of the weight loss. The polymer becomes prone to fragmentation and enzymatic surface erosion process.

Biodegradation of pure polycaprolactone in microbially active environments is very fast. The film was completely assimilated over the period of six weeks. This means that

polycaprolactone is very sensitive to enzymatic attack of microorganisms in living environments.

The processing additives to polycaprolactone slow down the degradation process in sea water environment.

References

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